

CONTROL OF HEAT TRANSFER ABILITY OF RADIATORS USING THERMOVALVE

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Abstract

The correct choice of equipment for the heating system, their effective use is important in providing the required amount of heat. In the heating system, the number of ribs of radiators is selected after calculation for the coldest day of winter. But the temperature of the external environment also changes during the heating season. Also, when calculating the required heat load for rooms, the amount of additional heat is not taken into account. In cases where the amount of heat released into the heated room and the transmitted heat flow is more than the norm, it can be controlled by means of thermal fans in the room itself, without affecting the operating mode of the heating system. After installing the radiator, it is necessary to pre-adjust the thermo valve in order to prevent the room from overheating the radiator or not being supplied with enough heat.

Keywords: heat load, heat carrier, mass consumption, total consumption, heat transfer ability, heating system useful work coefficient, heat capacity, thermal fan, heat flow.

1. Introduction

Each element of the modern heating system serves to increase the efficiency of the heating system. Creating optimal conditions in the room on cold winter days depends not only on the elements of the heating system, but also on the equipment of the room, the number of people gathered in the room at the same time, the number of lighting devices and several other factors. Building standards and regulations, as well as sanitary standards, set a number of requirements for indoor air parameters [1-2]. The first of the requirements for the parameters of the air in the room is the temperature. During the heating season, the use of a thermal fan provides a number of conveniences in keeping the air temperature in the room at a normal level [4-5].

2. Materials and Methods

The main purpose of building heating is to replenish the heat lost through the external walls, windows, doors, roofs and floors of buildings in the cold season of the year. The total amount of heat lost in the rooms is calculated. When calculating the heat of the barrier constructions, the calculation temperature of the outside air is selected based on the SRC [3]. The

heating period is determined, and when calculating the heat loss, the average temperature of the outside air is taken over the cold five days in winter. Based on the amount of lost heat, heating devices are used to establish the necessary temperature in the rooms. When performing calculations, we take into account the main part of the heat lost through the external barrier constructions, as well as the amount of heat lost in the direction of the light, ventilation and other additional heat. But heat flows into the room with the help of several factors. Heat flows entering the room are composed of the following:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n Q_{as} = Q_{peop} + Q_{sun} + Q_{ligh} + Q_{elec.motor} + Q_{bake} + Q_{mat} + Q_{etc} \quad (1)$$

here: Q_{peop} - heat from people; Q_{sun} - heat of solar radiation; Q_{ligh} - heat from lighting equipment; $Q_{elec.motor}$ - heat released from electric motors of machines and mechanisms; Q_{bake} - technological furnaces; Q_{mat} - from material cooling, etc.

If we take residential buildings, heat is released into the rooms from people, lighting equipment, stoves and other equipment.

Calculation of heat dissipation from people. Overt and latent heat is emanating from people. The flow of

these heats depends on the condition of people, that is, whether they are doing work in a calm, light, moderate, or heavy state.

Heat flux from one person, V_t .

Parameters	The number of parameters suitable for room air temperature, °C				
	15	20	25	30	35
Peaceful state					
Exposed heat	116	87	58	40	16
Full heat	145	116	93	93	93
Under conditions of defeat					
Exposed heat	122	99	64	40	8
Full heat	157	151	145	145	145
Medium weight in working conditions					
Exposed heat	133	104	70	40	8
Full heat	208	203	197	197	197
In difficult working conditions					
Exposed heat	162	128	93	52	16
Full heat	290	290	290	290	290

Note; The table shows the heat flow from men. Heat flux from men is assumed to be 85% and 75%, respectively, of heat flux from women and children.

Also, heat flow from lighting devices, baking ovens, gas stoves and similar devices is released into the rooms. The heat carrier supplies the necessary heat to the rooms. Depending on the type of heat carrier, there are heating systems that work with hot water, work with steam, work with hot air and work with gas.

Water and air heating systems are mainly used for heating in residential and public buildings. Air conditioners are usually used in the air heating system. When heating with the help of air conditioners, the required temperature is determined. If the air in the room exceeds the set temperature, the air conditioner will turn off automatically. When the temperature in the room drops below the set standard, the air conditioner starts again automatically. But in the water heating system, controlling the temperature in the room is a complicated process. In order to control the flow of heat transferred to one room, it is usually necessary to lower the temperature of the heat carrier prepared in the boiler unit. At the same time, the temperature of the heat carrier, which is transferred to the entire heated volume, decreases. In the rooms where the additional heat flow does not come, the air temperature drops below the norm. In order to prevent such situations, it is advisable to use thermal valves in the heating system. Thermovalve are used in heating systems and allow to control the level of heat

transfer of radiators without affecting the operation of heating boilers.

Figure 1. Heimeier-Vexact thermovalve

The main function of the thermal fan is to regulate the flow intensity of the heat-carrying water.

3. Results

Manual control of the heat transfer ability of radiators in the heating system with the help of a thermo-screw is observed on the basis of experience using the "Building heating system" stand.

Figure 2. "Building heating system" stand

The experimental work is carried out in the following order:

1. The building's heating system is filled with water.
2. The pump is set to the minimum level[6-9].
3. "Building heating system" stand is adjusted with an adjusting screw. let volume flow be 1 liter/minute.
4. The stand has radiators with 3-4-5 ribs. Water consumption in each radiator is determined using the Taco device.
5. The temperature of the water supplied to the system and the temperature of the outgoing water are measured. The temperature of the water supplied to the system was 70 0C, and the temperature of the water returning from the system was 55 0C.
6. The heat transfer capacity of a 3-rib radiator in the educational stand is 700 W, the heat transfer capacity of a 4-rib radiator is 1500 W, and the heat transfer capacity of a 5-rib radiator is 2100 W.

Calculations are made based on the obtained results.

$$m = \frac{Q}{c \cdot \Delta t} \quad (2)$$

Calculation results

The mass consumption for a 3-rib radiator is found:

$$m = \frac{Q}{c \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{700}{1,163 \cdot 15} = 40,1 \text{ kg/hour}$$

The mass consumption for a 4-rib radiator is found:

$$m = \frac{Q}{c \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{1500}{1,163 \cdot 15} = 86 \text{ kg/hour}$$

The mass consumption for a 5-rib radiator is found:

$$m = \frac{Q}{c \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{2100}{1,163 \cdot 15} = 120,4 \text{ kg/hour}$$

Table of record of obtained results

Number of radiators	t ₁ °C	t ₂ °C	Δt °C	V ts/kgK	m kg/hour
3-radiator	70	55	15	1,163	40,1
4-radiator	70	55	15	1,163	86
5-radiator	70	55	15	1,163	120

Figure 3. Flow and pressure diagram of the Heimeier-Vexact thermovalve

The value corresponding to the 3rd radiator is marked on the Y-axis and a green line is drawn parallel to the X-axis.

The thermovalve is adjusted to the appropriate level using a special key.

The value corresponding to the 4th radiator is marked on the Y-axis and a red line is drawn parallel to the X-axis. The thermovalve is adjusted to the appropriate level using a special key.

The value corresponding to the 5th radiator is marked on the Y-axis and a yellow line is drawn parallel to the X-axis.

The thermovalve is adjusted to the appropriate level using a special key.

Based on the obtained results, the thermostat can be adjusted as follows

Figure 4. The results obtained on the basis of the flow and pressure dependence diagram of the Heimeier-Vexact thermovalve.

Calculation results

3-rib radiator:

$$m = \frac{Q}{c \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{700}{1,163 \cdot 15} = 40,1 \text{ kg/hour}$$

For a radiator with 3 ribs, the set value of the thermostcrew is equal to 3.

4-rib radiator:

$$m = \frac{Q}{c \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{1500}{1,163 \cdot 15} = 86 \text{ kg/hour}$$

For a 4-rib radiator, the set value of the thermostcrew is equal to 5

5-rib radiator:

$$m = \frac{Q}{c \cdot \Delta t} = \frac{2100}{1,163 \cdot 15} = 120,4 \text{ kg/hour}$$

For a radiator with 5 ribs, the set value of the thermostcrew is equal to 6.

5. Conclusions

With the help of the "Building heating system" stand, the working principle of the thermo-screw was introduced. The heat transfer ability of radiators in the heating system depends on the temperature difference between the water supplied to the radiators and the water returning from the radiators, as well as the mass consumption of water. It is possible to control the heat transfer ability by changing the mass consumption of the water supplied to the radiators with the help of thermovintel. Choosing a thermostatic valve for the heating system, its correct adjustment has a significant impact on the efficiency of the heating system. In order for the heat transfer capacity of the 3-rib radiator to be equal to 700 W using the "Building heating system" stand, the mass consumption of water should be 40.1 kg/h, in this case, set the temperature screw indicator to 3, 4 - the mass consumption of water should be 86 kg/h in order for the heat transfer capacity of the ribbed radiator to be equal to 1500 W, in this case, setting the temperature screw indicator to 5, the heat transfer capacity of the 5-rib radiator is 2100 W to be equal to,

the mass consumption of water should be 120.4 kg/h, in that case, the indicator of the thermocoil should be set to 6. It is also possible to reduce the heat transfer ability of radiators by reducing the mass consumption of water during the hot days of the heating season.

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